

CALIBRATION OF STOCHASTIC, AGENT-BASED NEURON GROWTH MODELS WITH APPROXIMATE BAYESIAN COMPUTATION

Introduction

This document is the supplementary information for the article “Calibration of stochastic, agent-based neuron growth models with Approximate Bayesian Computation” by Duswald T., Breitwieser L., Thorne T., Wohlmuth B., and Bauer R. published in the *Journal of Mathematical Biology* (2024). This document accompanies the code base used to obtain the numerical results and is intended to explain how it may be used. We split the discussion thereof into the following parts:

- Computational requirements
- Dependencies and Docker
- Running a standard experiment
- Modify the code to run other experiments
- Necessary modification to adapt code base to calibrating own models

The code base combines different components to calibrate neuron models; however, we want to emphasize that it has yet to be developed into a full, user-friendly suite. That being said, we hope it still provides a meaningful starting point for further research endeavors.

Note that the presentation is likely slightly informal and colloquial.

Computational requirements

The implementation only supports CPU architectures; additional GPUs cannot accelerate the statistical inference. We conducted computational experiments on computing nodes with either 72 or 128 cores. The individual experiments typically took 3 to 7 days, depending on the sampling efficiency of the algorithm.

The implementation is MPI-based, so it should be possible to use multiple nodes to accelerate time-to-solution to some degree. However, we have not had access to such systems or explored/tested such capabilities.

To get started, we recommend using compute nodes of similar size.

Dependencies and Docker

The project has plenty of dependencies, many of which are inherited from other libraries. Most notably, the neuron growth models are simulated with BioDynaMo (<https://github.com/BioDynaMo/biodynamo>), and the calibration is conducted with Approximate Bayesian Computation algorithms implemented in abcpy (<https://github.com/eth-cscs/abcpy>). We use an interface constructed with glib to couple the two packages.

While we do not list all dependencies, we provide a Dockerfile / Docker image that encapsulates the project environment, including all necessary dependencies, and allows you to easily setup an

environment which is able to execute the code. This requires you to have docker set up and available on your system. The scripts assume sudo-less docker, i.e., we expect your user to be part of the docker group such that you can run docker without sudo privilege.

To begin with, you need to download the docker image `smcabc-reproducer-image-v1-docker-image-6a490e25c598.tar.gz` and the `code-base.tar.gz` from the zenodo repository. After unpacking the repository with

```
tar -xzvf code-base.tar.gz
```

You can load the docker image with

```
code-base/docker/load.sh smcabc-reproducer-image-v1-docker-image-6a490e25c598.tar.gz
```

Executing this command may take a few minutes. Alternatively, you may build the container yourself with `docker/build.sh`, which we do not recommend.

If you plan to launch a calibration run, we recommend that you now enter into a screen/tmux session because the calibration will take days, and you will want to disconnect from the server. After loading the docker image, you may now use it as a container by launching it with

```
cd code-base && docker/run.sh && docker/exec.sh
```

These commands spawn the container instance and let you enter into the interactive session.

Next, we build the main dependency — BioDynaMo with the following commands (requires internet connection) :

```
cd biodynamo && mkdir build && cd build && cmake -Dnuma=off -Dtest=off .. && make -j
```

After first use (new container, new `exec.sh`, ...), you must source BioDynaMo to be found by the computer. To do that, simply run

```
. bin/thisbdm.sh && cd ../..
```

We're now set to run a calibration experiment.

Running a standard experiment

We must first compile the forward model. Therefore,

```
cd neuronal_growth && bdm build
```

Once compiled (repeated calibration does not require rebuilding the application), we can launch the calibration with Wasserstein-ABC (recommended in a screen / tmux session):

```
mpirun -np <number of cores> --bind-to core --map-by L3cache python pysrc/optimization/smcabc_methods.py
```

The output is automatically logged to `smcabc_methods.log`, and the results are saved to the results folder with a date time stamp. On some servers, we encountered the issue of the application being unable to launch initially. If this is the case for you, repeat executing the above program until the simulations start running. The default parameters are such that we run the experiment associated with Fig. 7.

Once the calibration has concluded (according to some criteria), the calibration results are exported in the journal file (`*.jnl`). To visualize the convergence of the parameter inference, execute

```
python pysrc/analysis/plot_smcabc_convergence.py --journal results/smcabc-  
methods/<date-time-stamp>/experiment-<method>.jnl --n_steps 10
```

Wich will create a plot of the posterior distribution akin to Fig. 7 of the paper. Please investigate your folder structure to identify the placeholders; the latter is likely “wasserstein”.

Modify the code to run other experiments

The file `smcabc_methods.py` has many options that may be changed to run different experiments.

- The data can be modified in line 361.
- The hyperparameter, e.g., number of iterations, maximum number of simulations, etc. of the individual calibration runs may be adapted in the dictionary “`methods_parameters`”, starting from line 429 on.
- The type of distances are predefined in the script. Different choices can be made by changing “`skip = true`” to “`skip = false`” in the above mentioned dictionary. For anything else but predefined methods, we refer to the `abcpy` manual.
- QoIs / observations can be modified in line 368 onwards.
- Changing the parameters that need to be calibrated requires interacting with the function `infer_parameters` (line 128) and possibly the model wrapper (separate python file).

Necessary modification to adapt code base to calibrating own models

1. Implement model with BioDynaMo (or other compiled model taking command line arguments)
2. Understand valid parameter range and define priors
3. Adapt model wrapper to new model
4. Get appropriate data (recommended to begin with synthetic data generated via model implementation)
5. Run calibration